

Development of a Novel Liquid Chromatography Coupled to Multiple Reaction Monitoring (LC-MRM) Assay for the Quantification of Neurofilament Light Chain in Cerebrospinal Fluid and Comparison with Ultra-Sensitive Immunoassay: A Step toward Standardization

Salomé Coppens ^a and Christophe Hirtz^{a,*}

BACKGROUND: Neurofilament light chain (Nf-L) is a key early biomarker for axonal damage and neurodegeneration, increasingly used in clinical practice for diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment monitoring. To ensure reliable clinical implementation, standardized measurement procedures and calibrators traceable to the International System of Units (SI) are needed. Although a few mass-spectrometry methods for Nf-L quantification in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and plasma have been described, none currently use properly defined SI-traceable calibrators and existing harmonization efforts rely solely on immunoassays. This study presents a validated immunoprecipitation (IP)-LC-MS/MS assay using an SI-traceable calibrator and compares it with Lumipulse and Simoa platforms to assess agreement and bias.

METHODS: A new IP-LC-MS/MS method was developed based on SI-traceable calibrator quantification and analytically validated using International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines. Analysis of 69 CSF samples by MS assay and Lumipulse (Fujirebio[®]) was performed as well as head-to-head comparisons between MS, Simoa (Quanterix[®]) and Lumipulse assays on 12 CSF pools.

RESULTS: The method relying on 3 peptides was validated analytically. Significant results ($P < 0.05$) were obtained between amyloid positive to negative group when using the LC-MS/MS assay. MS and Lumipulse results

were correlated. Head-to-head comparison of the 3 methods showed great correlation ($r^2 > 0.98$) but systematic bias was identified between all techniques.

CONCLUSION: A new IP-LC-MS/MS method using a SI-traceable calibrator was developed, and analytically and clinically validated. Comparison between available immunoassays resulted in great correlation but biases were identified reinforcing the need of standardization for Nf-L measurement.

Introduction

The neurofilament light chain (Nf-L) is an increasingly used biomarker reflecting axonal injury and neurodegeneration in several neurodegenerative diseases. This structural protein is found in the axon of large caliber myelinated neurons and is part of a larger complex named Neurofilament (Nf). When axonal damage occurs, fragments of Nf-L are released into the interstitial fluid of the brain, the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and in much lower quantity into the bloodstream, rendering it measurable in those fluids (1, 2).

For many years, efforts have been made in to establish reference intervals, assess confounding factors such as aging, as well as to determine the pre-analytical variation of this biomarker (3). Nowadays, the use of Nf-L in routine clinical practice has increased considerably as its utility has been highlighted for diagnosis, as well as the prognostic and treatment monitoring of several pathologies (2). Multiple immunoassay kits and platforms are available for the quantification of this marker including, notably, the Uman Diagnostic (Quanterix) enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), single molecule array Simoa (Quanterix), Lumipulse (Fujirebio) that complies with the In Vitro Diagnostics Directive, Cobas (Roche[®]), Atellica (Siemens[®]), and Ella

^aPPC-LBPC, Univ Montpellier, INM, INSERM, IRMB, CHU Montpellier, Montpellier, France; ^bNational Measurement Laboratory, LGC, Guildford, United Kingdom.

*Address correspondence to this author at: Plateforme de Protéomique Clinique, IRMB—CHU de Montpellier—Hôpital Saint Eloi, 80 avenue Augustin Fliche, Montpellier 34295, France. E-mail c-hirtz@chu-montpellier.fr.

Received August 11, 2025; accepted November 17, 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/hvaf180>

(BioTechne®) (4). In addition, some reference intervals and cutoffs are already defined, bringing Nf-L closer to clinical implementation (5, 6). Although the use of this biomarker is widespread and the different kits correlate well, important differences in absolute values for CSF and blood Nf-L measurements exist between suppliers. This variability makes it difficult to define universally applicable cutoff values, complicates comparisons and follow-up across studies or centers, and increases the risk of misdiagnosis (7–10).

In this context, the quantification of Nf-L must be standardized through the development of a reference measurement procedure (RMP) and certified reference material for both matrices to achieve a universal decision limit, enable data comparison across laboratories and hospitals, and ultimately comply with the ISO17511:2020 standard for *in vitro* diagnostics once a higher-order reference material will be established (11). A candidate method based on liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) is already in development for Nf-L measurement in CSF (12).

To establish such a method, the measurand should be defined in biological fluids. Budelier et al. (13) demonstrated the presence of several fragments of the protein, especially fragments from the coil domains including coil 2, which contains peptides correlating well between the mass-spectrometry assay and immunoassay. In addition, a paper published by Meda et al. (14) highlighted the presence of multimers of the protein. Recently, another article was also published characterizing the commercially available full-length Nf-L protein as being a potential calibrator (15). In that study, authors elucidated several higher-order structures in the recombinant material within artificial CSF, demonstrating the capability of this protein to polymerize into multimers. This should be considered when a quantification method is developed.

Currently, only 2 mass spectrometry methods based on immunocapture at protein or peptide levels have been described for measuring Nf-L in CSF (13, 16) with 1 based on protein immunoprecipitation in plasma (17), but neither of them using properly defined and value assigned calibrators with a method traceable to the International System of Units (SI). In addition, while head-to-head comparisons and commutability studies have already been carried out for Nf-L to achieve harmonization, those were only based on immunoassay measurements (8, 9). Only 2 comparisons have been made between assays based on LC-MS/MS and an immunoassay, namely Uman Diagnostic's ELISA and Simoa that use the same pair of antibodies (13, 16). Therefore, additional studies including LC-MS/MS and using SI-traceable calibrators are required to support standardization by assessing feasibility, identifying potential issues such as poor correlation due to differences

in selectivity or measurand, and to evaluate the impact of recalibration by measuring interassay biases.

This article describes a new immunoprecipitation (IP)-LC-MS/MS assay for the quantification of Nf-L in CSF that will support and accelerate the current development of an RMP, using a previously characterized SI-traceable calibrator (15), validated analytically according to International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines and clinically on 69 CSF samples. This is followed by a head-to-head comparison of the Lumipulse and Simoa platforms with the LC-MS/MS method on 12 CSF pools to assess assay agreement and potential biases.

Materials and Methods

MATERIALS AND REAGENTS

Natural recombinant Nf-L protein and labeled (Lys and Arg ¹³C, ¹⁵N) recombinant Nf-L were purchased from Promise Proteomics. ADx 209 anti-Nf-L antibody was sourced from ADx Neurosciences. Trizma Base (Tris), ammonium sulfate, dimethylformamide, guanidium, monosodium phosphate (NaH₂PO₄), and disodium phosphate (Na₂HPO₄) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, trypsin/Lys-C from Promega, ammonium bicarbonate, and hydrogen peroxide 30% solution from Honeywell Fluka Analytical. acetonitrile, ultrapure LC-MS grade water, formic acid, and acetic acid from Biosolve, phosphate buffered saline (PBS) solution from Dutscher, sodium chloride (NaCl), and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) from VWR, and nonyl phenoxy-polyethoxyethanol (NP-40) from Alfa Aesar.

ANTIBODY DIALYSIS

Slide-A-Lyzer MINI 0.5-mL 10K molecular weight cut-off dialysis cartridge (ThermoFisher Scientific) membranes were cleaned with 100 mM phosphate buffer solution (prepared with 25 mM NaH₂PO₄ and 80 mM Na₂HPO₄) 3 times. In each, 50 μL of antibody at 2 mg/mL were mixed with 50 μL of 100 mM phosphate buffer. Cartridges were put into a tube containing 100 mM phosphate buffer and placed on a plate shaker for 2 hours at 0.1g. This step was repeated a second time after refreshing the buffer. As a result, 100 μL of dialyzed antibody was recovered.

BEAD COATING

For bead coating, 165 μL of Dynabeads M270 Epoxy (ThermoFisher Scientific) magnetic beads previously prepared at 30 mg/mL into dimethylformamide were transferred into a microtube placed on a magnetic rack. The supernatant was removed, and the beads were rinsed twice with 500 μL of 100 mM phosphate buffer. The supernatant was removed. The 100 μL of

dialyzed antibodies as well as 70 μL of 100 mM phosphate buffer and 130 μL of 3 M ammonium sulfate were added. The beads were stirred for 16 hours at 37°C by inversion mixing. Using the magnetic rack, the supernatant was removed, and the beads were washed with 1 \times PBS 3 times. Beads were resuspended in 660 μL of 1 \times PBS buffer at 7.5 mg/mL.

CSF SAMPLES

CSF samples of patients followed in neurology departments of Montpellier University Hospital and conserved in a biobank at -80°C were analyzed. Participants were retrospectively selected from the NeuroCognition Biobank at Montpellier University Hospital. This biobank includes biological samples—plasma and CSF—collected from patients who were enrolled at the Resource and Research Memory Center between 2007 and 2016. All participants provided written informed consent for their samples to be stored in a legally registered and ethically approved biological repository (authorization no. DC-2008–417), with the understanding that these samples could be used for future scientific research. First, 69 CSF samples were analyzed. Then, for interplatform comparisons, 12 pools of CSF samples with increasing Nf-L levels were analyzed.

CSF SAMPLE IMMUNOCAPTURE

Here, 400 μL of CSF spiked with 10 μL of internal standard at 100 ng/mL were oxidized with 1% final concentration of hydrogen peroxide, mixed with 400 μL of MB2% (40 mM Tris, 137 mM NaCl, 2 mM EDTA, 10 mM guanidine hydrochloride, 2% IGEPAL NP-40, pH 7.4), and 12 μL of ADx209-coated beads at 7.5 mg/mL, and incubated for 2 hours at room temperature with inversion mixing. The beads were then separated from the supernatant using a magnetic rack and the supernatant was discarded. Beads were washed 3 times with 1 mL of 25 mM ammonium bicarbonate and resuspended into 50 μL of 25 mM ammonium bicarbonate before digestion.

QUALITY CONTROLS (QCS) PREPARATION

Pooled CSF samples were used as QCs. Low and medium NfL QC concentrations were 1000 and 2000 pg/mL. High and very high QCs were spiked with 1.32 and 2.33 ng, respectively, of recombinant Nf-L protein to reach 5000 and 8000 pg/mL.

TRYPTIC DIGESTION

CSF samples and QCs were both digested by adding 0.5 μg of trypsin/Lys-C and incubated overnight into a thermoshaker at 37°C at 450 rpm. Digestion was stopped with addition of 1 μL of 100% FA.

CALIBRATION CURVE PREPARATION

An eight-point calibration curve was generated in solution with different concentration of natural Nf-L and a fixed concentration of labeled Nf-L prepared in 100 μL of 25 mM ammonium bicarbonate. Points were digested with 0.5 μg of trypsin/Lys-C and injected in triplicate ranging from 0 and up to 20 ng of SI-traceable natural Nf-L with a fixed quantity of 4 ng of labeled Nf-L.

LC-MS/MS ANALYSIS

CSF samples were analyzed by injecting 45 μL into a Shimadzu 8060nx triple quadrupole instrument coupled to an inert Nexera LC40-D XSi (Shimadzu) respectively. The analytical column was a metal-free Shim-pack Scepter C18 3.0 μm , 2.1 \times 150 mm (Shimadzu). Mobile phase A was composed of water and 0.5% acetic acid and mobile phase B of acetonitrile and 0.5% acetic acid. Column oven temperature was set to 50°C. The chromatographic gradient started with 5% B and increased from 5% to 40% B in 22 minutes and up to 90% for 2 minutes before equilibration. The flow rate was set to 250 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Data were acquired in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode. Three Nf-L peptides (natural and labeled) were monitored (Supplemental Table 1). Source parameters were the following: heat block temperature 400°C, DL temperature 250°C, interface temperature 350°C, focus voltage 2 kV, heating gas flow 15 L/min, nebulizing gas flow 3 L/min, drying gas flow 3 L/min, desolvation temperature 600°C, and collisionally induced dissociation gas pressure of 300 kPa.

ANALYTICAL VALIDATION

Analytical validation of the newly developed LC-MS assay was performed according to ICH guidelines (18) and included the analysis of 4 CSF QC levels in 5 replicates over 3 days. Validation criteria were linearity ($r^2 \geq 0.98$, repeatability [coefficient of variation (CV) $\leq 15\%$ and CV $\leq 20\%$ for low QC], accuracy (85%–115% and 80%–120% for low QC), intermediate precision (CV $\leq 15\%$ and CV $\leq 20\%$ for low QC). Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) as well as carry-over and labeled contribution were also evaluated.

IMMUNOASSAYS MEASUREMENT

The 69 CSF samples were first diluted 20 times in 1 \times PBS and were analyzed using the Lumipulse platform (Fujirebio) with the G NfL kit.

The 12 QC levels were also analyzed using the Lumipulse as well as the Simoa v1 (Quanterix) kits.

Table 1. Summary of the validation results for 3 peptides.^a

Peptides	Linearity	Accuracy (%)	Repeatability (%CV)	LOD (pg/mL)	LOQ (pg/mL)	Intermediate precision (%CV)
GM(ox)NEALEK	[0.98–0.99]	[76–98]	[2–12]	103.81	207.62	[6–11]
QLQELEDK	[0.98–0.99]	[59–99]	[2–16]	118.07	236.14	[6–14]
EYQDLLNVK	[0.98–0.99]	[82–99]	[1–13]	24.49	48.97	[6–12]

^aLinearity, accuracy, repeatability, and intermediate precision include maximum and minimum values obtained after the analysis of 5 replicates of each QC in 3 independent batches.

DATA ANALYSIS

LC-MS/MS data were visualized and analyzed using Skyline version 23.1 (MacCoss Laboratory, University of Washington, Seattle). Peaks were visually inspected to check for the presence of interferences and ensure specificity. Light/heavy ratio was calculated for each sample and endogenous Nf-L concentrations were calculated with each independent peptide based on an 8-point calibration curve generated with $1/x^2$ regression. Statistical analysis and graphs were generated with R Studio version 24.9.1. For group comparison, the Mann–Whitney test was used with age chosen as a confounding factor. Each independent peptide was used for comparison as well as the Z-score of the 3 peptides and the Lumipulse results. Clinical sample results obtained with 2 different methods (i.e., LC-MS/MS and Lumipulse) were also compared using a Spearman regression with a 95% confidence interval using each peptide as the quantifier. Finally, to compare the results of CSF pools across the different quantitative methods, a Passing–Bablok regression was fitted as well as a Pearson correlation. Bland–Altman plots were also established to assess potential bias across the tested measurement methods.

Results

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND ANALYTICAL VALIDATION

A new IP-LC-MS/MS method was developed for the monitoring of peptides previously selected and detectable in the CSF (Supplemental Table 1). Quantification was based on the ratio between the natural and labeled protein using a recombinant Nf-L protein previously characterized and quantified by amino acid analysis and exact matching isotope dilution mass spectrometry (see Supplemental Material and Method and Supplemental Table 2). This quantification revealed a protein content of $61 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 1 \mu\text{g/mL}$ at 95% confidence interval with complete amino acid agreement (Supplemental Fig. 1). Once developed, the IP-MS assay was analytically validated according to the ICH guidelines. In the CSF QCs, only 3 Nf-L peptides were detectable: GM(ox)NEALEK, QLQELEDK, and EYQDLLNVK. Validation parameters were assessed in

independent batches over 3 days: linearity, accuracy, repeatability, intermediate precision, LOD and LOQ, carry-over, and heavy-labeled protein contribution. Data are shown in Table 1 and the detailed validation data are available in Supplemental Table 3 and Supplemental Figs. 3–5. All peptides show excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.98–0.99$) and good precision [repeatability CV = (1%–16%), intermediate precision: CV = (6%–14%)]. GM(ox)NEALEK demonstrates good accuracy (76%–98%) and precision [repeatability CV = (2%–12%)] but has a moderate sensitivity (LOD 103.81 pg/mL, LOQ 207.62 pg/mL). EYQDLLNVK is the most sensitive (LOD 24.49 pg/mL, LOQ 48.97 pg/mL) with the highest accuracy (82%–99%). QLQELEDK has slightly lower accuracy (59%–99%) and higher variability. No carry-over was observed after injection of the higher QC level. The contribution of the heavy-labeled standard was assessed by checking the 0 ng/mL Nf-L calibration point, no peak was observed for the natural peptides.

CLINICAL VALIDATION ON PATIENT CSF SAMPLES

Clinical validation of the IP-LC-MS/MS assay for Nf-L quantification was performed on 69 CSF patient samples. Cohort characteristics are tabulated in Table 2 with patient diagnostics organized in 4 main groups: (a) Alzheimer disease (AD) group; (b) other neurological disorders (OND) (including hydrocephalus, epilepsy, brain cancer, vascular pathologies); (c) other degenerative disorders (ODD) such as Parkinson disease, Lewy body dementias, frontotemporal dementias; and (d) controls.

Once acquired and integrated, the concentration of Nf-L was calculated using the calibration curves for each peptide. Nf-L concentrations were also measured using the Lumipulse. Diagnostic groups were compared using a Mann–Whitney *U*-test with age as a cofounding factor, using the 3 peptides as quantifier and the Lumipulse data (Supplemental Fig. 5). Overall, only AD and OND groups were significantly separated ($P < 0.05$) using GM(ox)NEALEK and QLQELEDK peptides set as quantifier and using the Lumipulse. Controls and ODD groups were not significantly separated.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the cohort.

Age (median [range])	71 [23–93]
Sex (M/F)	32/37
Amyloid status (+/–)	38/31
Diagnostics	
AD	30
OND	21
ODD	13
Control	5

Additionally, quantification of the 69 CSF samples allowed separation between amyloid positive and negative groups using the IP-MS method when GM(α)NEALEK peptide was used as a quantifier ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 1A). Other peptides did not separate the groups significantly (Fig. 1B and C). However, the mean Z-score of the 3 peptides was able to separate both groups (Fig. 1D) with $P < 0.05$. Nf-L quantification with the Lumipulse also demonstrated a significant difference ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 1E).

A receiver-operator characteristic (ROC) curve was generated to compare the 3 measurement approaches showing significant results, including IP-MS using GM(α)NEALEK as a single peptide, the Z-score of the 3 peptides or the Lumipulse (Fig. 1F). Areas under the curve were close between all 3 with the largest being the LC-MS method with GM(α)NEALEK as quantifier but not significantly different according to Delong test. Based on these results, GM(α)NEALEK was defined as the quantifier to be used in subsequent analyses. The others were used as qualifiers, meaning these peptides had to be detectable with an S/N ratio greater than 3 for the quantification to be validated.

DATA CORRELATION WITH LUMIPULSE

Further analyses were performed to determine the correlation between each peptide and the Lumipulse measurement (Fig. 2). A strong correlation was observed between them with $\rho > 0.85$. However, differences in terms of absolute values were highlighted with the IP-LC-MS/MS data, giving higher concentrations than the Lumipulse.

CORRELATION BETWEEN TWO IMMUNOASSAYS USING 12 CSF QC LEVELS

To further explore the correlation between different immunoassay platforms and the novel IP-LC-MS/MS

method developed, 12 CSF pools with different Nf-L levels were analyzed using the LC-MS method, the Simoa and the Lumipulse platforms. For each paired comparisons, a Passing–Bablok regression was fitted, and Pearson correlation calculated (Fig. 3). Overall, there was strong correlation between methods with $r_s \geq 0.99$. There was a systematic underestimation using immunoassays or overestimation using the IP-LC-MS/MS method for each comparison. This was particularly true for the comparison between Lumipulse and LC-MS (Fig. 3B) with a slope of 0.48 and negative intercept highlighting the bias. This is also the case when comparing both immunoassays (Fig. 3C). Finally, confidence intervals were quite narrow when comparing Lumipulse with both LC-MS and Simoa, in contrast to the comparison between Simoa and LC-MS.

Finally, Bland–Altman graphs were plotted to assess the agreement between 2 measurement methods by plotting their mean values against their differences (Fig. 4). Good agreement is obtained if differences are small and randomly scattered around zero, with a narrow limit of agreement.

All comparisons showed a bias between the methods with a respective positive mean bias of 1080 pg/mL for LC-MS/MS vs Simoa, 2459 pg/mL for LC-MS/MS vs Lumipulse and 1379 pg/mL for Simoa vs Lumipulse. These confirmed that LC-MS/MS values based on GM(α)NEALEK were consistently higher than both Simoa and Lumipulse (Fig. 4A–C) indicating systematic constant bias. Simoa values fell between LC-MS/MS and Lumipulse, the latter yielding the lowest concentrations. Proportional Bland–Altman analysis (Fig. 4D–F) showed uniform positive bias at across concentration levels, consistent with systematic overestimation by LC-MS/MS. These trends highlight a constant component of interassay disagreement.

Discussion

A NEW TARGETED MS BASED ASSAY VALIDATED FOR NF-L QUANTIFICATION IN CSF

In the present article, we describe a new LC-MS/MS method based on MRM acquisition for the quantification of Nf-L in CSF. This method uses an SI-traceable recombinant protein that was previously characterized by ensuring the metrological traceability chain. Furthermore, this recombinant protein was structurally characterized using various mass-spectrometry techniques that revealed a higher-order structure providing essential insights into its conformational properties and their potential impact on assay performance (15).

Analytical validation was carried out to assess method performance. The 3 selected peptides defined as the measurand are located on coil 2 of the protein rod

domain and were the only ones detectable and sensitive enough when measuring endogenous Nf-L. These peptides have already been highlighted in multiple studies, which reinforced the decision to develop and validate them (13, 16). Overall, all peptides showed excellent linearity and strong precision. EYQDLLNVK presented the best sensitivity and GM(ox)NEALEK performed well in accuracy and precision compared to QLQELEDK. Overall, all the peptides complied with the validation criteria and ICH guidelines, except for QLQELEDK, which exhibited lower accuracy and repeatability at low concentrations. As this method is not intended to become an RMP, these results are

acceptable, as they comply with the requirements for immunoassays. However, if this current method is proposed as a reference, additional criteria should be evaluated in the future, especially with regard to uncertainty. In addition, EYQDLLNVK is not proteospecific to Nf-L as it is shared with other intermediate filament proteins. Therefore, GM(ox)NEALEK was set as the quantifier peptide and EYQDLLNVK and QLQELEDK were defined as qualifiers to confirm the presence of the analyte.

To overcome this limitation due to the nonspecificity of the EYQDLLNVK peptide, it would be judicious to use another enzyme to cleave this peptide. Only Nf-L contains this peptide, which has a lysine on the N-ter

end (K/EYQDLLNVK), while the other proteins have an arginine (R/EYQDLLNVK). Using an enzyme that cleaves specifically after a lysine residue, such as Lys-C, would make it possible to release this peptide specifically. On the other hand, certain peptides such as GM(ox)NEALEK would no longer be cleaved.

In addition, the main limitation of our approach is the potential lack of commutability between the recombinant SI-traceable protein spiked in matrix used as the

calibrator and endogenous Nf-L in CSF as previously described in a publication by Andreasson et al. (9). While the recombinant protein was extensively characterized (15), differences in structural conformations may affect its behavior in the matrix and, by altering epitope accessibility, matrix interactions, or digestion efficiency, lead to differences in detection and quantification that ultimately impact measurement accuracy. Additionally, linearity was assessed in solvent, which

Fig. 4. (A–C), Bland–Altman plots: (A) comparison between the Simoa and LC-MS using GM(ox)NEALEK peptide as the quantifier; (B) comparison between the Lumipulse and LC-MS using GM(ox)NEALEK peptide as the quantifier; and (C) comparison between the Simoa and the Lumipulse; (D–F), Proportional Bland–Altman plots: (D) comparison between the Simoa and LC-MS using GM(ox)NEALEK peptide as the quantifier; (E) comparison between the Lumipulse and LC-MS using GM(ox)NEALEK peptide as the quantifier; and (F) comparison between the Simoa and the Lumipulse. The x-axis represents the mean value of the 2 measurements, the y-axis shows the difference between the 2 measurements either in absolute value (A–C) or in percentage (D–F), blue dashed lines correspond to the average difference between the 2 methods and the red dashed lines are the limit of agreement (LOA) corresponding to the 95% confidence intervals.

may not fully reflect matrix effects in CSF. Future studies should focus on further evaluating commutability and optimizing calibration strategies.

Despite these limitations, it represents a significant advancement in Nf-L quantification by integrating metrological traceability, ensuring robustness, and providing a well-characterized SI-traceable material. Further comparisons of this approach with existing LC-MS methodologies (13, 16) using different peptide quantifier will be valuable.

THE IP-LC-MS/MS SIGNIFICANTLY SEPARATES DISEASES AND AMYLOID GROUPS

To clinically validate our method, 69 CSF samples from the Montpellier Biobank were collected and analyzed using the LC-MS/MS method and the Lumipulse platform. Using the LC-MS/MS method with GM(ox)NEALEK or QLQELEDK as the quantifier peptide, we were able to measure Nf-L in patient samples and significantly distinguish AD from OND,

similar to the Lumipulse measurements. However, due to the variety of pathologies present in the different groups, Nf-L concentrations varied. Therefore, Nf-L concentrations were compared based on the amyloid status of the patients. Only GM(ox)NEALEK, set as the quantifier peptide, was able to differentiate between both groups. Both groups were also significantly separated when using the Z-score of the 3 peptides and the Lumipulse kit.

This study was conducted on a relatively small cohort with a high proportion of AD cases, but considerable heterogeneity in OND. The variability in Nf-L concentrations across different pathologies may affect the generalizability of the findings. To strengthen clinical validation, future studies should include a more diverse and balanced cohort, incorporating conditions such as frontotemporal dementia, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, and multiple sclerosis. In addition, comparisons with homogeneous disease groups and other biomarkers would further support the method robustness.

THE IP-LC-MS/MS CORRELATES WITH TWO IMMUNOASSAYS

The novel IP-LC-MS/MS method was compared with 2 widely used immunoassay platforms, Simoa and Lumipulse. To our knowledge, only Simoa and LC-MS/MS approaches have been compared previously (16), not LC-MS/MS vs Lumipulse as presented here.

The comparative analysis demonstrated a strong correlation across all measurement methods, with Pearson coefficients ≥ 0.99 . This high degree of linearity underscores the consistency of Nf-L quantification across platforms and validates the potential of IP-LC-MS/MS as a robust analytical approach for CSF Nf-L measurement.

Despite this strong correlation, notable systematic biases were observed, particularly through Passing–Bablok regression analysis and Bland–Altman plots. The slope of 0.48 in the Lumipulse vs LC-MS/MS comparison suggests a marked underestimation by Lumipulse or conversely, a potential overestimation by LC-MS/MS relative to each other. This bias was also evident in the comparison between the 2 immunoassays, indicating inherent platform-specific differences in absolute quantification. These results suggest that while relative trends are preserved, absolute values differ substantially between platforms.

The consistent positive biases in Bland–Altman analysis further confirmed those results. The LC-MS/MS with GM(ox)NEALEK set as the quantifier systematically yielded higher Nf-L concentrations than both immunoassays. Notably, the magnitude of disagreement increased with concentration, implying a proportional bias likely due to calibration differences or matrix effects that become more pronounced at higher analyte levels. This was already observed in a paper published by Vecchio et al. (19).

Interestingly, the narrow confidence intervals in the Lumipulse–LC-MS/MS and Lumipulse–Simoa comparisons suggested greater precision and less variability, particularly involving the Lumipulse platform. This might reflect tighter assay control or reduced susceptibility to matrix effects compared to the Simoa platform.

These findings emphasize the importance of cross-platform harmonization, particularly for clinical or longitudinal studies including treatment modifying therapies relying on absolute quantification of biomarkers. While IP-LC-MS/MS showed promise for its sensitivity and specificity, these systematic differences must be acknowledged and addressed, potentially through standardization efforts and the use of platform-specific reference ranges.

To conclude, this method reinforces the harmonization process around Nf-L measurement and supports the development of RMP based on LC-MS/MS method for Nf-L quantification in CSF and serum or plasma.

Supplemental Material

Supplemental material is available at [Clinical Chemistry](#) online.

Nonstandard Abbreviations: MRM, multiple reaction monitoring; Nf-L, neurofilament light chain; CSF, cerebrospinal fluid; IP, immunoprecipitation; ICH, International Council for Harmonisation; RMP, reference measurement procedure; NaH_2PO_4 , monosodium phosphate; Na_2HPO_4 , disodium phosphate; NP-40, nonyl phenoxy-polyethoxyethanol; QCs, quality controls; LOD, limit of detection; LOQ, limit of quantification; ROC, receiver-operator characteristic; AD, Alzheimer disease; OND, other neurological disorders; ODD, other degenerative disorders.

Author Contributions: *The corresponding author takes full responsibility that all authors on this publication have met the following required criteria of eligibility for authorship: (a) significant contributions to the conception and design, acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data; (b) drafting or revising the article for intellectual content; (c) final approval of the published article; and (d) agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the article thus ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the article are appropriately investigated and resolved. Nobody who qualifies for authorship has been omitted from the list.*

Authors' Disclosures or Potential Conflicts of Interest: *Upon manuscript submission, all authors completed the author disclosure form.*

Research Funding: This research received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program Marie Curie ITN "MIRIAD" under grant agreement number 860303. Part of the data was collected for the project 22HLT07 NEuroBioStand, which received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States (European Partnership on Metrology, 10.13039/100019599, 22HLT07 NEuroBioStand).

Disclosures: S. Lehmann has served on advisory boards for Roche Diagnostics, Biogen, Lilly, and Fujirebio.

Role of Sponsor: The funding organizations played no role in the design of study, choice of enrolled patients, review and interpretation of data, preparation of manuscript, or final approval of manuscript.

Acknowledgments: Mass spectrometry experiments were carried out using the facilities of the Montpellier Proteomics Platform (PPM, BioCampus Montpellier), a member of the national Proteomics French Infrastructure (ProFI UAR 2048) supported by the French National Research Agency (ANR-24-INBS-0015, Investments for the future F2030). The authors thank Eugene Vanmechelen from ADx Neurosciences for providing the antibody. We also thank Susanna Schraen from Lille University for providing CSF pools.

References

1. Yuan A, Rao MV, Veeranna, Nixon RA. Neurofilaments and neurofilament proteins in health and disease. *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol* 2017;9:a018309.
2. Barro C, Chitnis T, Weiner HL. Blood neurofilament light: a critical review of its application to neurologic disease. *Ann Clin Transl Neurol* 2020;7:2508–23.
3. Khalil M, Teunissen CE, Lehmann S, Otto M, Piehl F, Ziemssen T, et al. Neurofilaments as biomarkers in neurological disorders—towards clinical

- application. *Nat Rev Neurol* 2024;20:269–87.
- Coppens S, Lehmann S, Hopley C, Hirtz C. Neurofilament-light, a promising biomarker: analytical, metrological and clinical challenges. *IJMS* 2023;24:11624.
 - Hviid CVB, Knudsen CS, Parkner T. Reference interval and preanalytical properties of serum neurofilament light chain in Scandinavian adults. *Scand J Clin Lab Invest* 2020;80:291–5.
 - Simrén J, Andreasson U, Gobom J, Suarez Calvet M, Borroni B, Gillberg C, et al. Establishment of reference values for plasma neurofilament light based on healthy individuals aged 5–90 years. *Brain Commun* 2022;4:fcac174.
 - Forgrave LM, Ma M, Best JR, DeMarco ML. The diagnostic performance of neurofilament light chain in CSF and blood for Alzheimer's disease, frontotemporal dementia, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Alzheimers Dement* 2019;11:730–43.
 - Ashrafzadeh-Kian S, Figdore D, Larson B, Deters R, Abou-Diwan C, Bornhorst J, et al. Head-to-head comparison of four plasma neurofilament light chain (NfL) immunoassays. *Clin Chim Acta* 2024;561:119817.
 - Andreasson U, Gobom J, Delatour V, Auclair G, Noam Y, Lee S, et al. Assessing the commutability of candidate reference materials for the harmonization of neurofilament light measurements in blood. *Clin Chem Lab Med* 2023;61:1245–54.
 - Mondésert E, Schraen-Maschke S, Quadrio I, Bousiges O, Bouvier D, Delaby C, et al. A French multicenter analytical evaluation of the automated Lumipulse G sNfL blood assay (Fujirebio®) and its comparison to four other immunoassays for serum neurofilament light chain assessment in clinical settings. *Clin Chim Acta* 2025;565:120007.
 - International Organization for Standardization. ISO 17511:2020—In vitro diagnostic medical devices—Requirements for establishing metrological traceability of values assigned to calibrators, trueness control materials and human samples. <https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/69984.html> (Accessed July 2025).
 - Mavrina E, Kimble L, Waury K, Gogishvili D, Gómez De San José N, Das S, et al. Multi-omics interdisciplinary research integration to accelerate dementia biomarker development (MIRIADE). *Front Neurol* 2022;13:890638.
 - Budelier MM, He Y, Barthelemy NR, Jiang H, Li Y, Park E, et al. A map of neurofilament light chain species in brain and cerebrospinal fluid and alterations in Alzheimer's disease. *Brain Commun* 2022;4:fcac045.
 - Meda FJ, Knowles K, Swift IJ, Sogorb-Esteve A, Rohrer JD, Dittrich A, et al. Neurofilament light oligomers in neurodegenerative diseases: quantification by homogeneous immunoassay in cerebrospinal fluid. *BMJ Neurol Open* 2023;5:e000395.
 - Coppens S, Gogishvili D, Faustinelli V, Scollo E, Hopley C, Abeln S, et al. Neurofilament light chain under the lens of structural mass spectrometry. *ACS Chem Neurosci* 2025;16:141–51.
 - Leckey CA, Coulton JB, Giovannucci TA, He Y, Aslanyan A, Laban R, et al. CSF neurofilament light chain profiling and quantitation in neurological diseases. *Brain Commun* 2024;6:fcac132.
 - Coulton JB, He Y, Barthelemy NR, Jiang H, Holtzman DM, Bateman RJ. Multi-peptide characterization of plasma neurofilament light chain in preclinical and mild Alzheimer's disease. *Brain Commun* 2024;6:fcac247.
 - European Medical Agency (EMA). ICH guideline M10 on bioanalytical method validation. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/ich-m10-bioanalytical-method-validation-scientific-guideline> (Accessed May 2025).
 - Vecchio D, Puricelli C, Malucchi S, Virgilio E, Martire S, Perga S, et al. Serum and cerebrospinal fluid neurofilament light chains measured by SIMOA™, Ella™, and Lumipulse™ in multiple sclerosis naïve patients. *Mult Scler Relat Disord* 2024;82:105412.